

Considerations in the Design of Naval Electric Power Systems

CDR John V. Amy Jr, U.S. Navy

Abstract—A discussion of the historical approach to the design of U.S. Navy naval electric power systems offers insight into advanced approaches for the design of future naval electric power systems. The unique characteristics of naval electric power systems are discussed, especially with regards to how they contrast with commercial utility power systems. In light of the background and uniquenesses, the basic questions confronting the designer of naval electric power systems are offered.

Index Terms—power systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recognition of the necessity and ubiquity of shipboard electric power and control systems, the expense of their modification, and the ephemeral nature of a significant number of mission loads, shipboard electric power system design represents an investment in a ship's long-term infrastructure. The design of naval electric power systems is best approached from that perspective which contrasts with the traditional approach of designing such systems to support only the anticipated loads at the time of ship construction. Similarly, allocation of the naval electric power system commodity, electricity, through controls which implement command directed priorities offers the benefit of being the most responsive approach to fulfilling the objective of a naval electric power system which is to provide power to all vital loads.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Historical

USS Trenton, built in 1878, had two propulsion systems, sail and steam. Its new feature was an electric lighting system, circa 1883. This lighting system was the first U.S. Navy ship service electric power system. Following this start, in the successive decades, came the wireless radio, heating and ventilation, proliferation of electric motors, radar, sonar, analog computers and then the power electronic revolution. Naval electric power systems have been sized on the basis of the ships' estimated electric loads. If installed ship service electric power capacity is a metric of the magnitude of the ship service electric loads, then, since **USS Trenton's** debut,

electric loads on warships have grown from bare kiloWatts, in 1883, to the order of 10megaWatts one-hundred and twenty years later, an increase of at least four orders of magnitude. (Fig. 1 of [1] captures this remarkable increase and is provided below.) This points to the enormous growth, even in just the last thirty years, in the use of and dependence upon electric power on naval ships. One just has to look in the commercial vessel trade literature to discern a similar trend there.

Figure 1

Sailing ships' propulsion system could not provide power for any use but propulsion. Steam ships eventually integrated the power systems installed in them, propulsion and ship service electric, at the point of steam generation. Even in the turboelectric ships prior to and during World War II, propulsion and ship service electric power were provided by distinct electric generators. In virtually all other ships, excepting diesel submarines, propulsion and ship service electric power were almost always provided by separate prime movers. Where these two power systems are provided for by common generators, the power system is said to be integrated electric. Where they are not provided by common generators, the power system can be said to be segregated. For the most part, contemporary U.S. Navy practice is to employ segregated power systems.

B. Naval Electric Power Distribution System

Essential to understanding how contemporary naval electric power systems are intended to operate is recognizing the distinction between "vital" and "non-vital" electric loads. Vital loads are so important that they are provided with connections to two sources of electric power. Particularly vital loads have an automatic bus transfer switch which will, upon

CDR J.V. Amy Jr., PhD, U.S. Navy, is Associate Professor of Naval Construction and Engineering with the Ocean Engineering Department of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, MA 02139 USA.

sensing loss of its primary power source, automatically switch the particularly vital load to its alternate power source. Vital loads that are not “particularly vital” have a manual bus transfer switch which allows a Sailor, who notices that such a load’s primary power source is not providing power, to switch the load to its alternate power source. Non-vital loads are provided with connections to only one source of power. Electric loads are hard wired to their source(s) at the time of the construction of the vessel. How “vital” they are is determined at that time and does not change unless the power system hardware is modified. This is how electric loads are prioritized.

Naval ships are designed to withstand tremendous amounts of damage and continue to remain afloat and operate. The strategy to achieve this survivability within U.S. Navy ships is to employ redundancy and separation of vital systems. This has led to ship service electric power systems which employ a “ring bus” set of interconnections between the ship service electric generators. The “ring bus” was successful in allowing restoration of power after loss of a generator and other equipment. The loads located throughout the ship are fed from the “ring bus” via switchboards which are located on the “ring bus”, then load centers, distribution panels and power panels in a radial topology. Loads within geographic zones of the ship are fed from distribution points that are located within that zone and feed that zone exclusively. “Vital” loads have two sources of power and, hence, represent an intersection of two radial branches. The two sources of power are separated longitudinally, one forward and one aft. The classic U.S. Navy ship service electric power system is a radial, low (440Vac) or medium (4160Vac) voltage, ungrounded, three phase, 60 Hertz system with air core circuit breaker protection. Small amounts of 400 Hertz power are also provided by a small distribution system.

In recent years, beginning with **USS Oscar Austin** (DDG 79), the U.S. Navy has moved from a radial topology to a “zonal” topology. In this topology, longitudinal feeders running the length of the ship on either side allow power to be provided from the generators. Within the geographic zones, power is provided to loads from either the port or starboard side longitudinal feeder, or, in the case of “vital” loads from a bus transfer switch connected to both. The **USS San Antonio** (LPD 17) Class amphibious transport dock ship will have a zonal distribution system as will the CVNX Class aircraft carrier. Zonal electric power distribution has become the U.S. Navy standard. Still, though, loads are hard wired according to the “vital”, particularly vital or not particularly vital, or “non-vital” distinction. The U.S. Navy ship service electric power system is still low (440Vac) or medium (4160Vac or 13.8kVac) voltage, three phase, 60 Hertz system. Small amounts of 400 Hertz power are still provided, although increasingly in a point-of-use manner. Other changes being pondered are adopting high impedance grounding and vacuum circuit breakers, as well as providing other forms of electric power for loads.

The contemporary design approach for naval electric power

systems is simply to twice apply a twenty percent margin to the maximum estimated ship service load and ensure that ninety percent of the rated capacity of one less than the installed number of identical generators is greater than that estimated maximum. With this generating capacity and number of generators determined, a zonal topology is employed and cabling and switchgear is sized based upon the estimated rating and proposed location of equipment. The nature of a load, whether it is particularly vital, not particularly vital but still vital, or non-vital, is still determined by its hard wired connection to sources and will not change unless the power system hardware is modified..

C. Analytic Approach

The U.S. Navy’s Integrated Power System (IPS) Program, [2]-[6], provided a functional analysis and architecture for future naval electric power systems, which will be assumed here. Six functions must be performed by the naval electric power system: control, generation, distribution, conversion, energy storage and utilization. How these functions are discharged will form the basis for examining proposed naval electric power systems.

Transport of a military mission, payload or cargo is the fundamental function of a ship. The ship’s power system is what makes this happen. Without a power system, a ship is just a barge. A ship’s power system is a design driver of the first order, both in terms of performance and expense. Power systems are expensive to buy and install and generally remain unaltered for the service life of the ship. This implies significant life cycle cost effects. The power system is one of the heaviest systems of the ship and is an intensive user of space and volume and location.

Given the importance of a ship’s power system, the efficiency and performance that can be achieved by constructing a single, integrated power infrastructure to last the service life of the ship make very good arguments in favor of integrated electric power systems. Much has been written extolling the benefits accruing to integrated electric power systems, it is largely true and will not be repeated here. With some possible exceptions, it is assumed that integrated electric power systems are preferable for U.S. Navy warships.

Four assertions dictate that naval electric power systems be considered concurrently with their own and the ship’s command and control system. First, all ships have electric power systems.--They are necessary to perform the ship’s function. Second, electric power systems on ships are different than terrestrial utility power systems and require different analytic approaches. Third, the state of the art technology in ship electric power systems is changing from an electromagnetic/electromechanical basis to a power electronic basis. Fourth, the demand for high-performance systems can be fulfilled only through utilisation of computer controlled actuators. These assertions lead one to conclude that relying upon hard-wired characteristics of an electric power system to provide satisfactory behaviour during perturbations will no longer provide satisfactory performance of the crucial electric

power system.

A consequence of the foregoing is that an object oriented approach for analysis of naval electric power systems is assumed. Information exchange and energy flow both affect dynamics and both must be considered as state variables with non-zero, off-diagonal elements of the system Jacobian matrix. In other words, an information 'signal' can 'cause' a large power flow.

III. UNIQUE CHARACTERISTICS OF NAVAL ELECTRIC POWER SYSTEMS

A. Analytical Uniquenesses

A naval electric power system, especially one that will fit inside of a warship, possesses some important characteristics when analysing its behaviour. First, cable runs are essentially limited by the length of the ship. Transmission line dynamics do not play a significant role. Second, the close physical proximity and 'close' electrical proximity of components means that control information is passed very rapidly between parts of the system. Third, the constraints and design practices relevant to naval electric power systems conspire to limit generating capacity and rotational inertia. In contrast, commercial electric power systems (speaking here of the U.S.'s) have thousands of generators which all contribute to capacity and inertia. By limiting generating capacity and rotational inertia onboard a warship, the characteristic of having single loads which are a significant fraction of the generating capacity of the system is added to the already complex nature of naval electric power systems.

TABLE I
SOME CHARACTERISTICS OF TRADITIONAL NAVAL ELECTRIC POWER SYSTEMS

CHARACTERISTICS OF NAVAL ELECTRIC POWER SYSTEMS
Very little rotational inertia relative to loads
Fast controls maintain frequency.
Shipboard prime movers typically are faster than utilities' relative to dynamic times of interest.
Large, dynamic loads relative to generation
Generators share loads in proportion to rating.
Very fast load-sharing information is provided to all generators.
Power electronic switching loads figure considerably.
Transmission lines are not nearly as significant as for utilities.
IMPLICATIONS OF THESE CHARACTERISTICS
Typical electric power system models are not usually appropriate for analysing shipboard dynamics. Higher-order models are necessary both for generators and loads. For example, "Swing" equation assumptions are not met.
Some of the mathematical expediciencies used in usual electric power system analyses cannot be used with naval electric power systems. "Infinite" buses and "slack" buses do not have manifestations in naval electric power systems. Constant voltage", "constant frequency" and "constant power" simplifications are normally invalid.

Naval electric power systems are very tightly coupled both electrically and with mechanical systems.

Faults must be modelled consistently with the characteristics of naval systems.

Related to the issue of limited generating capacity and rotational inertia is the fact that naval electric power system prime movers are smaller than commercial electric power system prime movers. The smaller prime movers have time constants which are much closer to the generators' electrical time constants than is the case in commercial systems. Time scale separation in commercial electric power systems is well established and yields quite acceptable results. Time scales of naval electric power systems are not so easily separated.--In fact, mechanical and electrical dynamics are very strongly coupled. Table I and much of this discussion follow [7].

The small size, lack of inertia, tight coupling and 'close' electrical proximity of naval electric power systems require fast frequency and voltage controls. During parallel operation, load sharing information is provided to all on-line generators very rapidly. Generator loads are not scheduled; rather, loads are shared in proportion to the generators' ratings. Load flow formulations have little meaning. Further, the primary and secondary levels of control found in commercial systems are not present as such in naval electric power systems.

Loads onboard naval combatants are large, dynamic and rapidly applied. Given the lack of inertia and despite the fast controls, there are large excursions in voltage levels and frequency compared to commercial electric power systems, [8]. Additionally, while the ship service power system and emergency power system attempt to ensure that power is available to "vital" loads, in contemporary systems there are power interruptions during the switching to alternate sources and during the period of time it takes to start up prime movers, particularly the emergency generator. Constant voltage level, constant frequency, and constant power injection assumptions cannot be made for dynamic analyses.

This characterisation of naval electric power systems is much abbreviated and points out the significant differences between naval electric power systems and commercial electric power systems. The differences stem from different functions with different concomitant optimisations. The differences are driven, at the very least, by the disparate scales of the two types of power system.

B. Unique Perturbations to Naval Electric Power Systems

Much of the faulted analyses and fault tolerance work done for commercial, and naval, electric power systems supposes a probabilistic failure of a single component. The component can be a power carrying component, or possibly a control element. Some analysis considers the cascading effects, if any, of the initial single component failure.

For over two decades, naval electric power systems have also been analysed to assess their performance subsequent to 'battle' damage, the result of hostile action. The supposition behind assessing the effects of battle damage is that they are geographically imposed. Instead of a probabilistic single

component failure being a trigger, a probabilistically determined geographic area of the electric power system is 'damaged'. Within the damaged radius, all equipment, controls and distribution infrastructure is assumed destroyed, or at least non-functional. Multiple 'short' or 'open' circuits are expected to occur simultaneously at the moment of damage. Hence, the trigger event affects equipment, connections and the control system. Examining the cascading effects of this system perturbation is, therefore, different.

Whereas the provision of electric power to vital loads is necessary for both mission accomplishment and the safety of life, assuring satisfactory performance subsequent to geographically imposed damage is an important system design concern. In view of recent events, the commercial utility system design may seek to ensure its performance subsequent to hostile action. The function of shipboard electric power systems is to supply power to vital loads; now, the clause is added, despite damage to the system caused by hostile action. The damaged analysis conducted for naval electric power systems assumes that all equipment in the damaged area is no longer operational; hence, electric power loads within the damaged area no longer require electric power regardless of their priority, i.e., how "vital" they are. Consequently, a new set of load priorities emerges subsequent to damage. Besides the structural changes to load priorities caused by damage, the operation of the ship itself will motivate load priority changes after damage. Just prior to a weapon hit, the ship's self defense systems may have top priority; just after the weapon hit, the ship's damage control systems will probably have top priority, and so on. Hence, load prioritization will change over the many time scales associated with the electric power system.

C. Objective of Naval Electric Power Systems

The designer of a naval electric power system is attempting to optimise the delivery of energy (electric power) to vital loads despite faults, component failures, errors, pulsed dynamics and hostile disruptions. However simple this objective is to state, realising it involves very complex analysis. Naval electric power systems must be operationally available, reliable, survivable, efficient and flexible. As yet, there has been no articulation of an objective function which naval electric power systems designs would seek to optimise. This is in contrast to the profit function of commercial electric power systems.

IV. CONSIDERATIONS IN THE DESIGN OF NAVAL ELECTRIC POWER SYSTEMS

An integrated electric power system is assumed here. This is justified by viewing electric power as a commodity to be provided by an infrastructure. Both survivability and efficiency argue for an integrated infrastructure.

A. The first consideration confronting the designer of an integrated electric power system for a naval ship is how much power capacity to install.

Historically, with an allowance for load growth proportional to the anticipated loads at the time of ship construction, naval ship electric power generating capacity has been determined by the anticipated loads which will be installed at the time of ship construction.

The historical background indicates that the magnitude and specifics of electric loads on naval ships vary significantly over several different time scales. Loads are added and removed over the service life of the naval ship, thirty-five to fifty years. Loads are brought on line and taken off line over the course of a deployment, days to months. Loads vary from hour to hour and minute to minute in response to any number of operational, environmental, administrative or maintenance reasons. Some loads are controlled by computer; hence, the load realized by the system can be controlled by the system.

Pursuit of design flexibility in the three time frames argues for power allocation based upon command directed load prioritization in real time. This approach to power allocation contrasts with the traditional approach for implementing power allocation through inflexibly installed equipment, equipment parameters and configuration. This approach to power allocation underscores the dual aspect of naval electric power systems; namely, information AND energy are interconnected and interdependent. This approach to power allocation implies that the capacity for generation and distribution of electric power be somewhat independent of the specifics of the anticipated loads at the time of ship construction; the power system would be as inherent to the ship's design as the hull and would be intended to provide quality performance for the life of the ship with little need for modification.

B. The second consideration confronting the designer of an integrated electric power system for a naval ship is to develop the distribution architecture.

The initial assumption here selects an integrated power system over a segregated power system. Subsequent architectural selections must consider distribution topology, namely zonal, multi-level or something else. Radial topologies are classic and no longer considered to be effective. Combinations of topologies warrant consideration. For example, the type of power that is generated may be distributed to some loads and the ship-wide distribution system using a "ring bus"; the ship-wide distribution system may be zonal AC or DC and so on.

C. The third consideration confronting the designer of an integrated electric power system for a naval ship is to determine how much of what type of electric power will be provided by the ship-wide electric power system to loads.

For instance, will the ship-wide system provide only Type I power, Type I and III power, or Type I and III and several varieties of DC power? (Type I power is three phase, 440Vac, 60Hz power. Type III power is three phase, 440Vac, 400Hz power. Further details and definitions are provided in [8].)

Existing technology allows diverse power types to be provided from a single, integrated electric power system. This fact argues for the articulation of electric power interface standards. Such standards permit equipment vendors to employ their proprietary capabilities to compete with other vendors on a playing field which is equitable for them. Technologies that can be applied to the power conversion function are economic and performance drivers for the integrated electric power system. Resolution of the question of how much of what kind of power to provide has wide ranging cost and performance implications.

D. A fourth consideration confronting the designer of an integrated electric power system for a naval ship is to determine energy storage capacity.

This consideration is assumed to be associated with the need for some shipboard equipment to have uninterrupted power during an electric power system perturbation. If uninterrupted power is a requirement, then a logical provider is the integrated electric power system. The first consideration for energy storage is how much power must be uninterrupted. This provides a rate for discharge of the energy storage capacity. The second consideration for energy storage is how much energy must be stored. This is related to how long an interruption in the provision of generated electric power must be 'bridged'. Back to the argument in favor of real-time power allocation, load prioritizations would certainly influence which loads should receive 'bridging power'. This approach would make 'bridge' capacity an electric power system infrastructure quality. Efficiencies and the ability to apply real-time load prioritizations argue in favour of this approach. It would constitute a "lead free" UPS.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Naval electric power systems are complex and interdependent. In ships, they are ubiquitous and an absolute necessity for mission accomplishment. Integrated electric power systems offer performance and flexibility available from no other architecture. Real time load prioritisation is an essential feature for advanced shipboard electric power systems. For the U.S. Navy to realise the full benefits of available technology, electric power interface standards must be defined to enable wide vendor participation. Considerable research into the information/energy or controls/power duality needs to be funded and conducted.

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VII. BIOGRAPHY

CDR John V. Amy Jr., USN graduated from the U.S. Naval Academy with a B.S. in E.E. in 1983, and served as Anti-Submarine Warfare Officer on *USS Boone* (FFG 28). He then reported to M.I.T. where he earned a S.M. in E.E. & C.S. in 1990, a Naval Engineer degree in 1990, and a Ph.D. in naval electric power systems in 1992. An Engineering Duty Officer, he subsequently was Assistant Project Officer for Aircraft Carrier Overhaul at Supervisor of Shipbuilding, Conversion and Repair, USN Newport News, VA. assigned to the refueling complex overhaul of *USS Enterprise* (CVN 65) and its subsequent post-shakedown availability. His next assignment was to the Engineering Directorate at the Naval Sea Systems Command. His specific assignment was initially Assistant Program Manager for Systems Engineering/Ship Integration within the Advanced Surface Machinery Programs, then subsequently Deputy Program Manager for the Integrated Power Systems Program (PMS 510). Following this, he attended Advanced Program Manager's Course at Defense Systems Management College. Upon graduation, CDR Amy worked next in the program office of the CVNX Program, the Navy's Future Aircraft Carrier Program. As Deputy Assistant Program Manager for Requirements and Test & Evaluation, he supervised aspects of the technical integration of new electric power technologies into the CVNX design. CDR Amy is presently a member of the M.I.T. faculty, Associate Professor of Naval Construction and Engineering, where, among other duties, he teaches courses covering naval architecture, marine engineering and naval ship design..